

Raport statystyczny

RNFLT in groups

RNFLT righth

```
str(dane %>% dplyr::select(OP.av, OP.S, OP.I, OP.T, OP.N))

'data.frame':  40 obs. of  5 variables:
 $ OP.av: chr  "55" "72" "82" "66" ...
 $ OP.S : chr  "64" "83" "108" "94" ...
 $ OP.I : chr  "57" "82" "82" "61" ...
 $ OP.T : chr  "48" "56" "55" "52" ...
 $ OP.N : chr  "53" "66" "84" "58" ...

dane <- dane %>%
  mutate(across(matches("^OP\\."), ~ parse_number(as.character(.),
                                                    locale = locale(decimal_mark = ","))))

dane_OP <- dane %>%
  filter(group %in% c("NTG", "HTG", "K")) %>%
  select(group, OP.av, OP.S, OP.I, OP.T, OP.N) %>%
  pivot_longer(cols = -group, names_to = "Zmienna", values_to = "Wartosc")
%>%
  mutate(group = factor(group, levels = c("NTG", "HTG", "K")))

srednie_OP <- dane_OP %>%
  group_by(Zmienna, group) %>%
  summarise(
    Średnia = mean(Wartosc, na.rm = TRUE),
    SD      = sd(Wartosc, na.rm = TRUE),
    .groups = "drop"
  )

p <- ggplot(srednie_OP, aes(x = group, y = Średnia, group = Zmienna, color =
Zmienna)) +
  geom_line(linewidth = 1) +
  geom_point(size = 3) +
  geom_errorbar(aes(ymin = Średnia - SD, ymax = Średnia + SD), width = 0.15)
+
  labs(x = "", y = expression("RNFLT right ["*mu*"m]"), color = "") +
  theme_minimal() +
  scale_color_manual(
    values = c(
      "OP.av" = "#1b9e77",
      "OP.S"  = "#d95f02",
```

```

"OP.I" = "#7570b3",
"OP.T" = "#e7298a",
"OP.N" = "yellow"
),
labels = c(
  "OP.av" = "Avarage",
  "OP.S" = "Superior",
  "OP.I" = "Inferior",
  "OP.T" = "Temporal",
  "OP.N" = "Nasal"
)
) +
scale_x_discrete(labels = c("NTG" = "NTG", "HTG" = "HTG", "K" = "Control"))

```

```
print(p)
```



```

ggsave(
  filename = "1trend_OP_prawe_oko.png",
  plot = p + theme(
    panel.background = element_rect(fill = "white", color = NA),
    plot.background = element_rect(fill = "white", color = NA)
  ),
)

```

```
width = 8, height = 5, dpi = 300
)
```

RNFLT left

```
str(dane %>% dplyr::select(OL.av, OL.S, OL.I, OL.T, OL.N))
```

```
'data.frame':  40 obs. of  5 variables:
 $ OL.av: chr  "68" "86" "72" "70" ...
 $ OL.S : chr  "72" "92" "105" "92" ...
 $ OL.I : chr  "95" "112" "64" "77" ...
 $ OL.T : chr  "42" "71" "47" "55" ...
 $ OL.N : chr  "63" "68" "71" "53" ...
```

```
dane <- dane %>%
  mutate(across(matches("^OL\\.\\.\\."), ~ parse_number(as.character(.),
    locale = locale(decimal_mark = ","))))
```

```
dane_OL <- dane %>%
  filter(group %in% c("NTG", "HTG", "K")) %>%
  select(group, OL.av, OL.S, OL.I, OL.T, OL.N) %>%
  pivot_longer(cols = -group, names_to = "Zmienna", values_to = "Wartosc")
%>%
  mutate(group = factor(group, levels = c("NTG", "HTG", "K")))
```

```
srednie_OL <- dane_OL %>%
  group_by(Zmienna, group) %>%
  summarise(
    Średnia = mean(Wartosc, na.rm = TRUE),
    SD      = sd(Wartosc, na.rm = TRUE),
    .groups = "drop"
  )
```

```
p <- ggplot(srednie_OL, aes(x= group, y = Średnia, group = Zmienna, color =
Zmienna)) +
  geom_line(linewidth = 1) +
  geom_point(size = 3) +
  geom_errorbar(aes(ymin = Średnia - SD, ymax = Średnia + SD), width = 0.15)
+
  labs(x = "", y = expression("RNFLT left ["*mu*"m]"), color = "") +
  theme_minimal() +
  scale_color_manual(
    values = c(
      "OL.av" = "#1b9e77",
      "OL.S"  = "#d95f02",
      "OL.I"  = "#7570b3",
      "OL.T"  = "#e7298a",
```

```

    "OL.N" = "yellow"
  ),
  labels = c(
    "OL.av" = "Avarage",
    "OL.S" = "Superior",
    "OL.I" = "Inferior",
    "OL.T" = "Temporal",
    "OL.N" = "Nasal"
  )
) +
scale_x_discrete(labels = c("NTG" = "NTG", "HTG" = "HTG", "K" = "Control"))

```

```
print(p)
```



```

ggsave(
  filename = "1trend_OL.png",
  plot = p + theme(
    panel.background = element_rect(fill = "white", color = NA),
    plot.background = element_rect(fill = "white", color = NA)
  ),
  width = 8, height = 5, dpi = 300
)

```

LGN in groups

right


```
p_box <- ggplot(dane_LGN_rh, aes(x = group, y = LGN_rh)) +  
  stat_boxplot(geom = "errorbar", width = 0.1, color = "black") + # krótkie  
  poprzeczki  
  geom_boxplot(  
    width = 0.55,  
    fill = "white",  
    color = "black",  
    outlier.shape = NA  
  ) +  
  labs(  
    x = "",  
    y = expression(LGN ~ right ~ volume ~ "[mm"3"]"),  
    title = ""  
  ) +  
  scale_x_discrete(labels = c("NTG" = "NTG", "HTG" = "HTG", "K" = "Control"))  
+  
  theme_minimal(base_size = 12) +  
  theme(panel.grid.minor = element_blank()) +  
  expand_limits(y = 50)
```

```
# podgląd  
p_box
```



```
# zapis do pliku  
ggsave(  
  filename = "LGN_right_boxplot.png",  
  plot = p_box +  
    theme(  
      panel.background = element_rect(fill = "white", color = NA),  
      plot.background = element_rect(fill = "white", color = NA)  
    ),  
  width = 8, height = 5, dpi = 300  
)
```

left


```
p_box <- ggplot(dane_LGN_lh, aes(x = group, y = LGN_lh)) +  
  stat_boxplot(geom = "errorbar", width = 0.1, color = "black") +  
  geom_boxplot(  
    width = 0.55,  
    fill = "white",  
    color = "black",  
    outlier.shape = NA  
  ) +  
  labs(  
    x = "",  
    y = expression(LGN ~ left ~ volume ~ "[mm"3~*~]"),  
    title = ""  
  ) +  
  scale_x_discrete(labels = c("NTG" = "NTG", "HTG" = "HTG", "K" = "Control"))  
+  
  theme_minimal(base_size = 12) +  
  theme(panel.grid.minor = element_blank()) +  
  expand_limits(y = 50)
```

p_box


```
ggsave(  
  filename = "LGN_left_boxplot.png",  
  plot = p_box +  
    theme(  
      panel.background = element_rect(fill = "white", color = NA),  
      plot.background = element_rect(fill = "white", color = NA)  
    ),  
  width = 8, height = 5, dpi = 300  
)
```